

EFFECTIVENESS OF SMART BOARD IN ENGINEERING LANGUAGE LABORATORY

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Abstract. *The elements and initiatives for digitization in the realm of education are covered in this article. It also skims over the benefits and difficulties associated with the creation of Smartboards in the digital age. Smart boards are an absolute necessity for those working in the digitalization industry, and they also pose a bigger professional development challenge. Smartboard use is encouraged and promoted by digitalization in all spheres of life. The idea that education and the sophisticated abilities needed to use technologies in various aspects of life are closely related is perplexing. This technological tool must be used by the higher education sector to accomplish the goal as effectively as possible. There has been a radical shift brought about by technical advancements in several fields.*

Keywords: *Creativity, Digitalization, Smartboard, technology, Visualization*

Introduction: The importance of adopting cutting-edge teaching technology and using it has become imperative in today's globalized society. Different technical tools are employed in engineering colleges and universities, and students are treated as digital learners the present generation of skilled users of digital technology. A significant shift was brought about by the use of the Smart Board tool. Studies that examined the use of technology in colleges and its effectiveness found that the use of technology is efficient for students (Anderson & Dexter, 2005) Utilizing technology enhanced the outcomes and assisted the students in making use of the resources employed as teaching and learning aids. Pupils find the materials visually appealing and much value the procedure. They see these technologies as efficient pedagogical vehicles for conveying the study material through tools that create a great deal of interest in the lesson (Dror & Gershon). The majority of students said that using technology to learn improves their motivation and overall experience. Using smart boards for learning makes it easier to access a wide range of resources that support knowledge acquisition, effective assignment completion, comprehension of the subject matter, and information organization.

Every once in a while, a new technology, an old problem, and a big idea turn into an innovation- Dean Kamen.

Digital learning has a massive impact on the education system as a whole. The dynamics of society are changing and it is time for teachers and students to redefine their communication techniques.

Digital learning assists students in subject learning. It enhances their overall performance integrating digital learning in class benefits students and teachers as well. (Lin, Chen, & Liu, 2017)

Smartboard refers to a specific interactive whiteboard technology that is developed by the company SMART TECHNOLOGIES.

It enhances the educational process while improving the quality of life for teachers. Students and teachers can work together to learn. They can operate software, transfer files, and access online resources. It has also been demonstrated that the technology, which is increasingly being used in universities around the nation, keeps students interested in their studies.

Today tools that help teachers capture and keep students’ attention are invaluable. A 2022 study by Gallup found that digital tools are strongly associated with better student outcomes including ease of learning from home and expectations for the learning process.

Adapting to various learning styles and increasing student engagement are two benefits of smart board learning. A kinesthetic, aural, or visual learner can all benefit from the interactive board. By highlighting specific themes using text or writing on the screen, educators may create more engaging classes. It is possible to share multimedia content on smart boards, including webpages, films, and picture presentations.

It offers boundless possibilities for combined learning. Teachers can more easily incorporate distant pupils using videoconference technology when they have smart boards. This makes hybrid learning possible. On standardized tests, students who used whiteboards performed noticeably better than those who did not. Paintings, symbols, screen designs, and other visual materials boost learning permanence.

Smartboard technology in the classroom can enhance student comprehension of the content by transforming a dry lecture into a lively, participatory learning environment. Classrooms are becoming more active learning environments thanks in part to smart boards and interactive and collaborative learning settings. The use of smart boards includes possibilities offered by the regular whiteboard, together with other means that enable interactive teaching-learning.

(Manny- Ikan, Dagan, Tikochinski, & Zorman,2011)as well as connecting to students’ Computers from home(Hadad& Gazit, 2012)

Blau (2011) listed three characteristics that transform the smart board into an efficient pedagogical tool:

- Divergent learning---- the ability to skip from pages on the screen to the internet in a structured and fluid manner. This ability simulates the associative organization of the student’s brain and contributes to the organization and clarity of the lesson as perceived by the student.
- Smartboards serve as a cognitive tool that expands student’s minds and facilitates supported joint thinking. Since some of the mental load is transferred from the students to the board, they are free to engage in higher thinking processes.
- Interactive learning--- Smart boards enable interactions between study contents and the students themselves, both face-to-face and online.

Teachers who use Smartboards in their lessons receive specialized training that teaches them how to use and manage the tool, such as aligning text with visual aids or minimizing needless explanations. For both teachers and pupils, regular boards are less practical and efficient. Additionally, the usage of smart boards displays the study material and even shows it more effectively, despite the technological challenges associated with controlling the board. Smartboards make it possible to project short films, images, and textbook pages that best illustrate the subject matter for the students. This helps the students learn the information and participate actively in class.

In a questionnaire on attitude to learning students in smart classrooms claimed that the smart board encourages motivation to learn, raises the level of concentration, and has a strong effect on behavior(Shuck& Kearney, 2007).

Advantages of using a smart board in the classroom

- It is simple, easy, and inexpensive.
- Provide solutions to the teacher’s problems
- Interactive teaching tools

- Smooth controls
- Improves student motivation and engagement
- Promotes retention and growth of concepts taught
- Smart boards turn ordinary classrooms into active learning centers.
- Teach larger groups of children with ease.
- Personalized learning
- Access previous notes
- Students enjoy high success rates
- An eco-friendly teaching method
- Using a learner-centered approach to teaching
- Increase students’ participation
- Low maintenance
- Better Brainstorming sessions
- Heightened retention of key points
- Technology integration
- Real-time assessment
- Enhanced learning experience

Disadvantages of smart board

Students who studied in smart classrooms claimed that there were often technical problems and that the teachers were not sufficiently proficient.

However, the disadvantages and advantages appear to be rooted in the teacher and student’s use of smart boards. The efficiency of smart boards depends on wise use by the teachers, to make the material accessible for the students. Teachers must teach how to use smartboards, prepare themselves well for each lesson, and use all the aids available to them. (Hadah& Gazit, 2012)

Smartboard in Language Lab

Usage of smartboards in English Language lab especially in engineering colleges is very useful and effective. Teaching phonetics has become very simple and informative. Students have been able to focus on listening to various phonemes and improve their pronunciation with stressed rhyme patterns. Even Advanced Communication skills have been given practice with the help of Smartboard. Group Discussions, JAM, Debate, Public Speaking, PowerPoint presentations, resumes, Letter writing, Dialogue Writing, and Statement of Purpose are some examples taught in the laboratory using Smartboard that reaches the students in a lucid and crystal clear manner.

Technology can become the wings that will allow the educational world to fly farther and faster than ever before; if we allow it. - Jenny Arledge

The twenty-first century will usher in an era of limitless technological advancement. Technology is consuming every nook and cranny in this period of rapid development. Tablets, computers, and smartphones are no longer foreign terms. Because this generation of students is not bound by the confines of simple learning and has a huge curiosity that cannot be satisfied by educational systems that were built earlier, the education system is evolving during this phase for the sake of improvement. We would deny the pupils their tomorrow if we continued to instruct them in the same manner as we did yesterday. In the 21st century, our antiquated educational system has no hope of survival. Therefore, digitization is important across all domains of education.

Conclusion

College students like smart board teaching methods but generally they prefer a combination of various methods including traditional and smart board teaching to understand concepts better. Overall, all of them unanimously agreed that they like smart board teaching and that it is comparatively easy to use. Students agreed that smart boards help them during lectures. Teachers are ready to adapt and blend various techniques to teach effectively by blending traditional as well as smartboard media. Teachers are expecting more digital improvements and enrichments

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